

2-Benzoyl-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles

R. A. KULKARNI* and S. R. THAKER

O. C. Shroff Research Institute, Goregaon (W), Bombay-400 062

Manuscript received 7 January 1987, accepted 12 April 1988

Preparations of some 2-benzoyl-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles are described.

α -Bromo-substituted-deoxybenzoins were condensed with benzoylmandelothioamide^{1,2} in presence of sodium acetate to obtain the benzoyl derivatives of 4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolylphenylcarbinols. These were hydrolysed and then oxidised to obtain 2-benzoyl-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles³ (Scheme 1).

Various benzophenone derivatives show strong bacteriostatic properties but having high toxicity^{4,5}. In the present series, one of the phenyl rings was substituted by a thiazole nucleus so as to prepare a series of new compounds having less toxicity but the same or enhanced antibacterial activity.

The series of reactions involved are

Experimental

The following α -bromodeoxybenzoins⁶ were prepared: α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 55°), 4'-methyl- α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 87°), 4'-chloro- α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 67.5°) and 4'-methoxy- α -bromodeoxybenzoins (72.5°).

Benzoyl derivatives of 4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolylphenylcarbinols. General procedure: Benzoylmandelothioamide (13.5 g, 0.05 mol), α -bromodeoxybenzoins (0.05 mol) and sodium acetate (0.05 mol) in ethanol (50 cm³) were refluxed for ~3 h. The reaction mixture was then poured over crushed ice. The product separated as a gummy mass was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Hydrolysis of the benzoyl derivative of 4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolylphenylcarbinols: Benzoyl derivative (10 g) was hydrolysed in 10% ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution. The product was poured into ice-water. The resulting gummy mass was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Oxidation of 4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolylphenylcarbinols: 4-Substituted-phenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolylphenylcarbinol (3 g) was oxidised to ketone by potassium dichromate (2 g) and acetic acid (30 cm³). The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol in the form of long yellow needles (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1	Benzoyl derivative of 4,5-diphenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	134	White shining crystals	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	78.15 (77.82)	5.08 (4.73)	3.10 (3.13)
2	Benzoyl derivative of 4-p-methylphenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	116	Cream thin needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ NO ₂ S	78.19 (78.06)	5.43 (5.02)	3.12 (3.03)
3	Benzoyl derivative of 4-p-chlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	128	White thin needles	C ₁₉ H ₉ ClNO ₂ S	72.22 (72.26)	4.41 (4.18)	2.85 (2.90)
4	Benzoyl derivative of 4-p-methoxyphenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	116	Cream thin needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ NO ₂ S	75.78 (75.44)	5.11 (4.85)	2.86 (2.93)

(Table 1 contd.)

5	4,5-Diphenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	154	White crystals	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ NOS	76.60 (76.94)	5.30 (4.99)	4.00 (4.08)
6	Hydrochloride of 5	163	White solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClNOS	69.03 (69.55)	4.52 (4.77)	3.26 (3.68)
7	4-p-Methylphenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	143	Cream shining crystals	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NOS	77.63 (77.28)	5.43 (5.35)	3.83 (3.91)
8	Hydrochloride of 7	153	White solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ClNOS	69.85 (70.12)	5.43 (5.11)	3.50 (3.55)
9	4-p-Chlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	140	White shining crystals	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClNOS	69.43 (69.92)	4.60 (4.26)	3.92 (3.70)
10	Hydrochloride of 9	158	White solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NOS	63.85 (63.77)	4.15 (4.13)	3.27 (3.88)
11	4-p-Methoxyphenyl-5-phenyl-2-thiazolyl phenyl carbinol	134	Off-white crystals	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	73.66 (73.96)	5.20 (5.12)	3.62 (3.75)
12	Hydrochloride of 11	147	White solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClNO ₂ S	67.50 (67.39)	4.85 (4.91)	3.15 (3.41)
13	2-Benzoyl-4,5-diphenylthiazole	128	Yellow shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ NOS	77.79 (77.39)	4.77 (4.43)	4.05 (4.10)
14	Oxime of 13	160	Colorless shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS	73.95 (74.13)	4.43 (4.52)	7.79 (7.85)
15	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of 13	132	Orange solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	64.15 (64.48)	3.39 (3.67)	13.15 (13.43)
16	2-Benzoyl-4-p-methylphenyl-5-phenylthiazole	120	Yellow shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ NOS	77.48 (77.71)	5.12 (4.82)	3.75 (3.94)
17	Oxime of 16	160	Colorless shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	74.70 (74.56)	5.00 (4.89)	7.44 (7.56)
18	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of 16	124	Orange solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	64.98 (65.03)	4.11 (3.95)	13.45 (13.07)
19	2-Benzoyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-5-phenylthiazole	126	Pale yellow shining leaflets	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClNOS	70.34 (70.30)	4.02 (3.75)	3.83 (3.72)
20	Oxime of 19	178	Colorless shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	67.40 (67.60)	3.93 (3.86)	6.98 (7.16)
21	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of 19	130	Orange solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ O ₄ S	60.35 (60.48)	3.45 (3.26)	12.71 (12.59)
22	2-Benzoyl-4-p-methoxyphenyl-5-phenyl thiazole	142	Bright yellow shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	74.41 (74.37)	5.00 (4.61)	3.68 (3.77)
23	Oxime of 22	158	Colorless shining needles	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	71.35 (71.48)	4.43 (4.69)	7.37 (7.24)
24	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of 22	138	Orange solid	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	63.46 (63.14)	3.64 (3.83)	12.90 (12.69)

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to the management of C. C. Shroff Research Institute for facilities. Sincere thanks are also due to Prof. L. P. Ghalsasi.

References

1. FRANCIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 1404.
2. J. F. OLIN and T. B. JOHNSON, *Recl. Trav. Chim.*, 1931, 50, 72.
3. J. F. OLIN and T. B. JOHNSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1470.
4. B. L. FREEDLANDER, *Am. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1944, 49, 543.
5. B. L. FREEDLANDER, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1949, 51, 153.
6. G. DREFAHL and H. GRAHMAR, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, 52, 17177.